

PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF ADOLESCENCE AND FACTORS OF HIS RESEARCH

Mamayusupova Iroda Khamodovna

Candidate of Psychological Sciences, teacher of the Department of Interfaculty Pedagogy and Psychology of KDPI

Email: irodamamayusupova7777@gmail.com phone: +99891 140-42-47.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12594344>

Abstract. *This article shows the solution to psychological problems associated with the upbringing and education of the younger generation, as well as changes in their attention, senses and imagination in early adolescence. During early adolescence, moral attitudes towards family and society provide information about what it means to realize the personal “I” on the basis of active activity.*

Keywords: *teenager, attention, stage.*

ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПОДРОСТКОВОГО ВОЗРАСТА И ФАКТОРЫ ЕГО ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ

Аннотация. *В статье показано решение психологических проблем, связанных с воспитанием и образованием подрастающего поколения, а также изменениями их внимания, чувств и воображения в раннем подростковом возрасте. В раннем подростковом возрасте нравственные отношения к семье и обществу дают информацию о том, что значит реализовать личностное «Я» на основе активной деятельности.*

Ключевые слова: *подросток, внимание, сцена.*

Psychological problems of the younger generation related to education and upbringing regularly attract the attention of prominent scientists, philosophers and writers. The first works of pedagogical and psychological content formed the basis of religious and moral teachings of the 17th-18th centuries. Examples of psychological research in Russia are formed in various works devoted to the human psyche under the influence of Eastern and Western culture. The initial views in the works of V.N. Tatishev, A.N. Radyshev, N.I. Novikov and others were influenced by the characteristics of mental development and differences in mental development.

Abu Rayhrn Beruni's thoughts on the purpose, objectives and status of education and training, human development and the younger generation are truly created on the basis of humanism and anthropology. The principles of natural harmony between education and upbringing can be observed in all the works of the thinker. He emphasizes that man is part of nature.

The book of the Russian historian V.N. Tatischev "Conversation about the benefits of sciences and the land of knowledge" shows the classification of sciences, the meaning of knowledge, the position of language and speech, their connection with the characteristics of youth.

Delving into the nature of outdoor education, age-appropriate learning exudes harmony with nature. In Beruni's pedagogical work, the main issues were man and his happiness, education and maturity. Middle Ages, his valuable information about the human psyche, the unity of body.

Early adolescence includes the developmental period of children from 15 to 18 years of age. These are students of academic lyceums and vocational colleges. During adolescence, physical qualities reached a relatively stable level. Early adolescence can be considered the second transition period. If the first transition is closer to childhood, then the second adolescent transition is closer to adolescence and is studied and researched in this regard. Early adolescence is predominantly characterized by the beginning of independent life. These life changes affect the personality and self-awareness of the early adolescent. Unlike teenagers. on the other hand, early adolescents do not imagine a big life, but perceive it. Along with his growing independence, his relationships with adults also change. Adults treat teenagers more like children, and they treat young teenagers like adults.

The first teenagers want to find their place in life.

Having become old enough, he begins to act to realize his life plans, chooses a certain profession or continues his studies in this field. Teenagers should not be considered adults.

Because childhood can be observed in their personality traits. This can be seen in their thoughts, lives and future relationships. Many teenagers are irresponsible when choosing a profession, even by the time they graduate from school. This period is characterized by the moral self-awareness of the teenager, as well as the transition to a new stage of morality. Teenagers with well-developed intelligence can understand and discuss issues that concern adults.

Teenagers ponder answers to many problematic questions. They are more interested in moral issues. If teachers are the source of solutions to moral issues for primary school students, then teenagers will look more for answers to these questions among their peers. Teenagers, in search of the correct answer to a question, turn to sources used by adults. Such sources are predominantly real, multifaceted, complex human relationships and scientific ones - popular fiction, journalistic literature, industrial works, the press, radio, television.

Today's teenagers have a cautious, intellectually practical outlook on life, freedom and independence. They are also realistic about the concept of righteousness.

are approaching. For example, as in previous years, they understand and interpret that "righteousness is not the same for everyone, but it is determined for each according to his

capabilities and for each according to his work or contribution to human interests.” By the time they graduate from school, many teenagers have already developed moral qualities and strengthened certain moral standards.

However, the process of self-education is not limited to the elimination of existing mental defects of a teenage student and the formation of positive qualities, but is aimed at developing content in accordance with the multifaceted, generalized ideal characteristic of adults.

Pupils try to consciously, plan, orderly, consistently and regularly acquire the most valuable qualities of a person, study and work skills, to develop certain qualities and characteristics of a person; they strive to solve the problems of self-education, to form a holistic spiritual and spiritual image.

The process of self-education of adolescent students must be within the framework of the educational influence of public organizations and the team of pedagogues. So that the improvement of self-education serves to occupy a worthy place in the team, to realize the social duty, and to involve in useful work. In order to put self-education on the right track, influence in the form of a complex of educational measures forming a harmonious unit is a collective commitment, mutual support and control, mutual evaluation and criticism. It is appropriate to do such things. It is the main task of the team of pedagogues to deal a severe blow to some forms of misbehavior, vices, and vices found in social life, to protect young men and women from their influence, and to fight against the nature of foreign propaganda.

Adolescents develop a sense of maturity and grow into a sense of self-determination and self-expression. This is expressed in their desire to recognize that they are a separate person. To do this, some young people try to show their fascinating interest in various fashions, complex visual industry, music, profession, and nature. Under the influence of educational and work groups, human qualities such as fortitude, courage, patience, humility, discipline, and honesty are improved, and vices such as selfishness, laziness, hypocrisy, indolence, laziness, cowardice, and ingratitude are eliminated. The role of public organizations in the process of personality formation of teenagers is of particular importance. In them, such qualities as activity, initiative, independence, determination, responsibility, critical evaluation of one's actions acquire a stable character. Active participation of young men and women in the community shows a certain organizational ability.

They seek to clarify who they are, what they are like, their abilities, what makes them respect themselves. He tries to understand who his friends and enemies are, his desires, what he needs to know in order to know himself and the world around him well. It is known that not all questions of teenagers are understood. Sometimes teenagers are never satisfied with themselves,

they have many tasks ahead of them, but they are not able to cope with them. It can be seen from these that teenagers reflect the depth of self-analysis and the need to fulfill high demands. This is one of the conditions for future success of teenagers.

Currently, a number of scientific and practical researches on the important problems of the psychology of youth and pedagogical psychology are being conducted by psychologists in our country. In the departments and laboratories of the leading universities of our republic, the research of the processes related to the psychological characteristics of youth and education is carried out effectively by highly qualified specialists in the conditions equipped with special techniques. The solution of these problems is taking its rightful place based on the methodological principles of modern science, having information about the achievements and ideas of scientific research conducted in this regard in near and far foreign countries.

REFERENCES

1. Xamidovna, Mamayusupova Iroda. "EVACUATION OF THE LEVEL OF CONFLICTS IN CONFLICT SITUATIONS BETWEEN ADOLESCENTS." *Confrencea 1.1* (2023): 23-27. <https://confrencea.org/index.php/confrenceas/article/view/372/375>
2. Khamidovna, Mamayusupova Iroda. "MASTERY OF MANAGING PEDAGOGICAL COMMUNICATION STUDY, GENERALIZATION AND DISSEMINATION OF ADVANCED PEDAGOGICAL EXPERIENCE." *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal* 10.12 (2022): 1217-1222. <https://internationaljournals.co.in/index.php/giirj/article/view/4627/4322>
3. Khamidovna M. I. CAUSES OF FAMILY CONFLICTS //Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2022. – T. 10. – №. 12. – C. 870-872. <https://internationaljournals.co.in/index.php/giirj/article/view/3156/2907>
4. Khamidovna, M. I. (2022). The influence of older people on the formation of the spiritual environment in Uzbek families. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(10), 360-364. https://api.scienceweb.uz/storage/publication_files/3062/8164/641d74df6fdbc_%D0%98%D0%BC%D0%BF%D0%B0%D1%84%D0%B0%D0%BA%D1%82%D0%BE%D1%8074_%D0%A0%D0%B0%D0%B2%D1%88%D0%B0%D0%BD%D0%B6%D0%BE%D0%BD2_%D2%9B%D0%B8%D1%80%D2%9B%D0%B8%D0%BB%D0%B3%D0%B0%D0%BD.pdf

5. Khamidovna M. I. THE CONCEPT OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGY //International journal of scientific researchers (IJSR) INDEXING. – 2024. – Т. 5. – №. 2. – С. 503-505.
https://scholar.google.ru/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=ru&user=sZY1_zEAAAAJ&citation_for_view=sZY1_zEAAAAJ:HDshCWyjkBEC
6. Khamidovna, Mamayusupova Iroda. "Psychological Advice On Preventing Conflicts Between Adolescents And Young People In The Family." Onomázein 62 (2023): December (2023): 2094-2100.
https://scholar.google.ru/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=ru&user=sZY1_zEAAAAJ&citation_for_view=sZY1_zEAAAAJ:qUcmZB5y_30C
7. Khamidovna, M. I. (2023). TYPES OF CONFLICTS BETWEEN ADOLESCENTS AND CONFLICT MANAGEMENT. Multidisciplinary and Multidimensional Journal, 2(5), 76-79.
https://scholar.google.ru/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=ru&user=sZY1_zEAAAAJ&citation_for_view=sZY1_zEAAAAJ:L8Ckcad2t8MC
8. ПОДРОСТКАМИ И. ЎСПИРИНЛАР ЎРТАСИДА НИЗОЛАР БИЛАН ЖАМОАДАГИ КОНФЛИКТ ВА УНИ ЕШИМГА ОЛИБ КЕЛИШ ЙЎЛЛАРИ //НАМАНГАН ДАВЛАТ УНИВЕРСИТЕТИ-2021. – Т. 1. – С. 592.
<https://scholar.google.ru/scholar?oi=bibs&hl=ru&q=related:YDC43xAG6B4J:scholar.google.com/>